

ການຫາສະພາວະທີ່ເໝາະສົມຂອງການຍ່ອຍສະຫລາຍເລືອງຂົ້າດ້ວຍເອນໄຊ SACCHARIFICATION OF IONIC LIQUID TREATED RICE STRAW

*Sengthong Lee ^(1,2), Virak Sorn ⁽²⁾, Keonakhone Khounvilay ⁽¹⁾, Khanok Ratanakhanokchai ⁽²⁾,
Paripok Phitsuwan ⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾ Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, National University of Laos, P.O. Box 3166, Sokpaluang Campus, 01005 Lao-Thai Friendship Rd, Vientiane Capital, Laos PDR

⁽²⁾ Division of Biochemical Technology, School of Bioresources and Technology, King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi, Bangkoktuen, Bangkok 10150, Thailand

*Corresponding author: lee.kee17@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Enzymatic saccharification of ionic liquid treated rice straw (IL-RS) was studied. Here, Box-Behnken based response surface methodology (BBD based RSM) was applied to find the suitable dosages of cellulase (Cellic® CTec2), xylanase (Cellic® HTec2) and Triton X-100 on hydrolysis of IL-RS. The result shows that cellulase and xylanase significantly affected (p -value < 0.05) the reducing sugar yields derived from the hydrolysis process of IL-RS. The experimental data obtained agreed with the predicted values ($R^2=0.98$), and the data were fitted to second-order polynomial equation. The maximal sugar yield was obtained with loads of Cellic® CTec2 at 50 FPU/g substrate, Cellic® HTec2 at 100 XU/g substrate, and Triton X-100 at 0.375 g/g substrate, giving reducing sugar 3,828.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 24-h incubation. Therefore, the model could be successfully used to identify the effective combinations of the three factors for increasing reducing sugar yield.

Keywords: *Rice straw, enzymatic saccharification, Response surface methodology, Box-Behnken design, optimization*

ບົດຄັດຫຍໍ້

ການຫາສະພາວະທີ່ເໝາະສົມໃນການຍ່ອຍເລືອງຂົ້າດ້ວຍເອນໄຊ ທີ່ຜ່ານການປັບສະພາບດ້ວຍທາດເຫຼວໄອໂອນິກໂດຍໃຊ້ວິທີພື້ນຜິວຕອບສະໜອງທີ່ມີການວາງແຜນການທົດລອງແບບບໍ່ອກເບນເຄນເພື່ອສຶກສາຜົນຂອງປະລິມານຂອງ 3 ບັດໄຈຄື ແຊລລູເລັດ, ໄຊລາເນັດ ແລະ TritonX-100 ໃນການຍ່ອຍເລືອງຂົ້າທີ່ຜ່ານການປັບສະພາບດ້ວຍຂອງເຫຼວໄອໂອນິກ. ຈາກຜົນການທົດລອງພົບວ່າ ແຊລລູເລັດ ແລະ ໄຊລາເນັດມີຜົນຢ່າງຊັດເຈນໃນການຍ່ອຍເລືອງຂົ້າທີ່ຜ່ານການປັບສະພາບ. ຂໍ້ມູນທີ່ໄດ້ຈາກການທົດລອງມີຄວາມເໝາະສົມກັບສົມຜົນ second-order polynomial ແລະ ເຫັນດ້ວຍກັບຄ່າການຄາດຄະເນ ເນື່ອງຈາກມີຄ່າສຳປະສິດຂອງການຕັດສິນໃຈສູງ ($R^2=0.98$). ສະພາວະທີ່ເໝາະສົມໃນການຍ່ອຍຟາງຂົ້າຄືໃຊ້ປະລິມານຂອງແຊລລູເລັດ 50 FPU/g substrate, ໄຊລາເນັດ 100 XU/g substrate ແລະ TritonX-100 0.375 g/g substrate ເຊິ່ງໃຫ້ຜົນຜະລິດຂອງ Reducing sugar ເຖິງ 3828.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ໃນເວລາການຍ່ອຍ 24 ຊົ່ວໂມງ. ສະນັ້ນ, ຮູບແບບໂມເດລສາມາດນຳໃຊ້ເພື່ອກຳນົດປະສິດທິພາບຂອງ 3 ບັດໄຈເພື່ອຄາດການຜົນຜະລິດຂອງນ້ຳຕານ reducing.

ຄຳສັບສຳຄັນ: ເລືອງຂົ້າ, ເອນໄຊ, ການຕອບສະໜອງແບບພື້ນຜິວ, Box-Behnken design

1. INTRODUCTION

Lignocellulosic biomass is being considered as the most abundant source of renewable energy and offers a great potential for development of high value-added products such as biofuels and biochemicals (Rocha-Martin, et al. 2017; Yang, et al. 2017). The main components of lignocellulose can be roughly classified into three main parts: cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The sum of cellulose and hemicellulose accounts for 70-80% of carbohydrates, which can be converted to fermentable sugar (Younas, et al. 2017; Diaz, et al. 2018). These three components are formed into a complex structure, that is, insoluble crystalline cellulose is embedded in a hemicellulosic matrix, where the hemicellulose side chains are linked to phenolic compounds to form lignin-carbohydrate complexes (Sorek, et al. 2014).

In conversions of the lignocellulosic biomass to bioproducts, enzymatic hydrolysis is a significant step to obtain high content of fermentable sugars. During this step, enzymes are determined as a high-performance catalyst and also reduce the corrosion of equipment and environmentally friendly (Duan, et al. 2017). The major enzymes involved in the hydrolysis of lignocellulose include cellulolytic (cellulase enzyme), hemicellulolytic (xylanase enzymes), and ligninolytic. The commercial enzymes Cellic® CTec2 (cellulase) and Cellic® HTec2 (xylanase) are complex enzyme mixture that widely utilized for the hydrolysis of pretreated lignocellulose materials for the conversion of the carbohydrates to simple sugars before fermentation (Novozymes 2010). However, the main challenge in cellulose hydrolysis is its low accessibility due to the residues of lignin after pretreatment process. It is also high enzyme loadings that constitute a significant contribution to the overall production cost. It is, therefore, important to find the condition on enzymatic hydrolysis to reduce enzyme loading and increasing conversion rate and yield.

To allow the enzymes access to the target substrates and make the enzymatic degradation of plant biomass more effective, many pretreatment methods, such as biological, acid, alkali, steam explosion, and ionic liquid treatments, have been developed (Taherzadeh & Karimi 2008; Gupta, et al. 2011; Agrawal, et al. 2017). Moreover, many researchers have reported that the addition of nonionic surfactants on enzymatic saccharification could enhance and increase the hydrolysis rate (Chen, et al. 2014; Qu, et al. 2017; Bukhari, et al. 2018). This is because the surfactant adsorbs on lignin via hydrophobic interaction (Liu, et al. 2016). It has shown that the positive effect of surfactants to promotes the cellulase accessibility to cellulose are blocking/reducing the non-specific enzyme-lignin interaction (Agrawal, et al. 2017; Luo, et al. 2019). The addition of Triton X-100 on enzymatic hydrolysis also increased the conversion efficiency of lignocellulosic biomass to soluble sugars (Cheng, et al. 2014). It was also reported that surfactants improved the efficiency of cellulose digestibility by increasing enzyme stability and modifying structure of substrates during enzymatic hydrolysis (Cao & Aita 2013; Vaidya, et al. 2014; Oladi & Aita 2018).

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a mathematical and statistical analysis, useful for modeling and analyzing problems where the response of interest is influenced by several variables for optimization process systems (JMP & Proust 2017). Box-Behnken Design (BBD) is a class of rotatable second-order design based on three-level incomplete factorial design. It can pinpoint a minimum or maximum response if one exists inside the factor region.

In the present study, rice straw pretreated by ionic liquid ([Bmin]Cl) was investigate with the commercial enzymes (Cellic® CTec2, Cellic® HTec2) and Triton X-100 to

optimize the enzymatic saccharification conditions for producing sugars by using RSM based on a second-order Box-Behnken design (BBD).

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Experiment apparatus and chemicals

The following experimental apparatus were used: High speed centrifuge VS-180CFi, Incubator with shaker, VORTEX mixer, Multiskan GO Microplate Spectrophotometer, Hotplate stiller or stiller, Hotplate Electrolux, Ice box.

The surfactant, TritonX-100 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The commercial enzymes cellulase Cellic® CTec2 (150 FPU/ml), and xylanase Cellic® HTec2 (1040 XU/ml) were purchased from Novozymes A/S, Bagsværd, Denmark.

2.2 Technique

2.2.1 Substrate and pretreatment

Rice straw (RS) was used as the substrate in this study. It was collected from rice fields in Thailand. Rice straw was pretreated with ionic liquid pretreatment according to Sorn, et al. 2019). A total of 0.25 g of RS powder was added to a 20-mL sample vial containing 5 g of [Bmim]Cl (ratio of 1:20). The RS/IL mixture in the tube was then heated at 130 °C in an oil bath by using a dry bath incubator (Major Science, USA) for 45 min. The ionic liquid pretreated rice straw (IL-RS) contains 35.53% cellulose, 17.19% hemicellulose, and 11.79% lignin.

2.2.2 Experimental design

A three-factor, three-level Box–Behnken design was used to optimize the hydrolysis conditions of IL-RS by deriving a second-order polynomial equation (1).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=i+1}^3 \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (1)$$

In which where ‘Y’ is the response (µg/mL), X_i and X_j are independent variables, β_0 is the constant, β_i is the represents the linear co-efficient, β_{ii} is implies the co-efficient of the squared terms, β_{ij} is the expresses co-efficient of the cross-term products and ‘k’ is indicates the number of independent factors.

For BBD design matrix, the concentrations of Cellic® CTec2 ranged from 5–50 FPU/g substrate, Cellic® HTec2 ranged from 10–100 XU/g substrate, and Triton X-100 ranged from 0.1–0.6 g/g substrate. They were considered as the variables and tested in 17 sets of experiments. As shown in Table 1, the three factors chosen for this study were designated as X1, X2 and X3 and prescribed into three levels, coded as +1, 0 and -1 for high, intermediate, and low values, respectively.

Table 1. Experimental design of the three factors and four variable Box–Behnken design.

Factors code	Factors (Units)	Levels		
		-1	0	+1
X1	Cellic® CTec2 (FPU/g)	5	27.5	50
X2	Cellic® HTec2 (XU/g)	10	55	100
X3	TritonX-100 (g/g)	0.15	0.375	0.6

2.2.3 Enzymatic hydrolysis

The enzymatic hydrolysis reactions were prepared in a 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube (Eppendorf tube). Each tube contained 5% (w/v) of IL-RS in 0.05 M sodium acetate buffer (ABS). The commercial enzymes cellulase (Cellic® CTec2), xylanase (Cellic® HTec2) and surfactant (TritonX-100) were added by different concentrations based on the levels of experiment design. The reaction mixture was then added with distilled water to a final total volume of 200 μ L. Then the reactions were incubated at 55°C in incubator with shaking speed 200 rpm, for 24 hours. After centrifuged at 10,000g, 4°C for 15 min. The supernatant was taken 100 μ L to the new eppendorf tube, and the amount of reducing sugar released from the substrate was determined by using the 3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) reagent method (Miller, 1959) with glucose as a standard. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm using a Thermo Scientific™ Multiskan™ GO Microplate Spectrophotometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA).

3. ANALYSIS

JMP version 13 (SAS Software) was used to develop the experimental model and estimate the co-efficient of the second order-polynomial. To determine the optimum factor levels for maximal yields, 3-D surface plots were utilized. In these 3-D plots, the optimum conditions were verified by conducting validation experiments comprising three independent experiments examining the responses generated in comparison to the model-predicted results. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for model prediction.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Optimization of enzymatic saccharification of ionic liquid treated rice straw

BBD based RSM was used to develop the experimental design to evaluate the optimal conditions for maximum yield of reducing sugar by studying the interaction effects of the enzymatic saccharification process of 3 variables: concentration of Cellic® CTec2 (X1), Cellic® HTec2 (X2) and TritonX-100 (X3), and their levels are presented in Table 1. Table 2 shows the levels of selected variables for the BBD employing with total 17 experimental runs and summarizes the response values along with the predicted values. The actual response reducing sugar from the experimental and predicted values from the model of IL-RS hydrolysis is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Actual versus predicted plot of response reducing sugar

The response obtained was calculated by second order polynomial regression equation for saccharification and it shows as below:

$$Y (\mu\text{g/mL}) = 2219.75 + 1036.86X_1 + 260.98X_2 + 34.266X_3 + 39.254X_1 * X_2 - 13.618X_1 * X_3 + 73.215X_2 * X_3 - 210.55X_1 * X_1 + 74.163X_2 * X_2 - 7.460X_3 * X_3 \quad (2)$$

Where Y is reducing sugar yield, X1 is the concentration of Cellic® CTec2, X2 is the concentration of Cellic® HTec2, and X3 is the concentration of TritonX-100. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out, which showed the linear, quadratic interaction and lack of fit of the response values of reducing sugars at various experimental conditions (Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 2. Experimental design and result of experimental reducing sugar yield after enzymatic saccharification

No	Variables factors			Response
	X1 (FPU/g)	X2 (XU/g)	X3 (g/g)	Reducing sugar ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
1	5	10	0.375	898.75
2	5	55	0.15	1210.01
3	5	55	0.60	1228.48
4	5	100	0.375	1391.26
5	27.5	10	0.15	2613.81
6	27.5	10	0.60	2583.99
7	27.5	55	0.375	2534.71
8	27.5	55	0.375	2528.00
9	27.5	55	0.375	2449.69
10	27.5	55	0.375	2589.37
11	27.5	55	0.375	2615.54
12	27.5	100	0.15	2591.73
13	27.5	100	0.60	2958.97
14	50	10	0.375	2883.93
15	50	55	0.15	3117.87
16	50	55	0.60	3344.95
17	50	100	0.375	3828.86

Table 3. Analysis of variances for the response

Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F Ratio
Lack of Fit	3	144299.88	48100.0	4.7956
Pure Error	4	40120.38	10030.1	Prob > F
Model	9	9387811.3	1043090	39.5923
C. Total	16	9572231.5	-	<.0001*

$R^2 = 0.9807$
 $\text{Adj } R^2 = 0.955$

*significant $p < 0.05$

Accordingly, the significance of the factors can be confirmed using p -value, which are statistical expressions used to indicate the significance of the model and variables. The models or variables with a p -value < 0.05 are considered significant, with a 95% confidence level. The model shows a low probability value ($p < 0.0001$) indicated that the model terms were significant. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value (0.98), a measure of the amount of variation around the mean, explained by the model indicated that only 2.0% of all variation for response could not be explained by the model and expresses a good fit. Three dimensional (3D) plots were generated using the appropriate model fitted using eq (2) to predict the relationships between independent variables and responses. Therefore, the model was applicable for predicting saccharification conditions in this study.

Table 4. ANOVA for the predicted model of reducing sugar concentration after enzymatic hydrolysis

*significant $p < 0.05$

These data demonstrated that X1 and X2 variables on saccharification conditions were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by each variable. The effect of X1 (Cellic® CTec2) was significant by ($P < 0.0001$) and the effect of X2 (Cellic® HTec2) concentration was significant ($P=0.026$), while the effect of surfactant was not significant ($P=0.5692$). Cellic®

Term	Estimate	Std error	t Ratio	Prob> t
Intercept	2219.75	72.58891	30.58	<.0001*
X1-cellulase	1036.86	57.38657	18.07	<.0001*
X2-xylanase	260.98	57.38657	4.55	0.0026*
X3-TritonX-100	34.266	57.38657	0.60	0.5692
X1*X2	39.254	81.15687	0.48	0.6434
X1*X3	-13.618	81.15687	-0.17	0.8715
X2 *X3	73.215	81.15687	0.90	0.3970
X1*X1	-210.55	79.10193	-2.66	0.0324*
X2*X2	74.163	79.10193	0.94	0.3797
X3*X3	-7.460	79.10193	-0.09	0.9275

CTec2 was the most significant variables because of very low probability values. There was an increase in reducing sugar yield with increased cellulase loading. In general, enzymatic hydrolysis of biomass requires a group of cellulase and xylanase enzymes. The commercial cellulase Cellic® CTec2 used for saccharification contained a significant amount of xylanase activity, which might act on the hemicelluloses part of the biomass and release sugars (Novozymes 2010; Singh & Bishnoi 2012). The interaction effect of X1*X1 was significant as well. Therefore, Cellic® CTec2 has more significant effect on the enzymatic saccharification than the others. The highest reducing sugar yields from IL-RS hydrolysis was obtained with a cellulase (X1) loading around 50 FPU/g biomass, xylanase (X2) 100 XU/g biomass, and with a TritonX-100 loading of 0.375 (g/g) (Table 2.).

Figure 2. Response surface plots representing the effect of X1 and X2 on enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS at 55°C for 24 h.

Response surface plots representing the effect of X1 and X2 on enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS (Fig. 2) shows that the reducing sugar concentration increased linearly according to the increase of cellulase (X1) concentrations. A high concentration of cellulase resulted in improved enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS. It also showed that xylanase (X2) improved the enzymatic hydrolysis at the high level of cellulase as well. It should be noted that X1 and X2 have a small interaction profile, increasing in cellulase loading has a large significant role on sugar yield.

Figure 3. Response surface plots representing the effect of X1 and X3 on enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS at 55°C for 24 h.

The predicted response surface for reducing sugar yields from IL-RS as functions of cellulase (X1) loading and TritonX-100 (X3) on enzymatic saccharification is presented in Fig. 3. It can be seen that even the surfactant concentration is varied in range of 0.15-0.6

g/g, but the reducing sugar yield is not increase. At the highest concentration of surfactant (X3) the reducing sugar was not increased. It could be indicated that the reducing sugar was increase as a linear depending on the cellulase (X1) and it does not have the interaction effects due to the low lignin contain in the substrate.

The response surface for reducing sugar yields from enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS as functions of xylanase loading (X2) and concentration of TritonX-100 (X3) is presented in Fig. 4. It was shown that the reducing sugar was increased with the concentration of X3 and X2 dosage ranges, the local maximum reducing sugar was obtained at the highest level of the design concentration of X3 0.6 g/g substrate and X2 100 XU/g substrate. In addition, the higher enzyme loading, the greater reducing sugar yields. The interaction of those variables were not significant by the interaction effects. The results also show that the addition of surfactant could increase the rate of enzymatic hydrolysis, especially at low enzyme loadings. The ability of nonionic surfactant to minimize nonproductive and irreversible binding of cellulose to lignin might be the reason for this benefit (Parnthong & Kungsanant 2014).

Figure 4. Response surface plots representing the effect of X2 and X3 on enzymatic saccharification of IL-RS at 55°C for 24 h.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present study highlights the primacy of rice straw as a feedstock for sugars production and bioethanol production. Response surface methodology was successfully applied to optimize enzymatic saccharification conditions of ionic liquid-pretreated rice straw by applying commercial enzymes and surfactant, Cellic® HTec2 and TritonX-100. Response surface plot in three-dimension obtained from the empirical quadratic model showed the interaction effect of two variables on the studied response and the optimum values of the selected variables. Optimal saccharification conditions were obtained using 5% of the IL-RS, Cellic® CTec2 at 50 FPU/g substrate, Cellic® HTec2 at 100 XU/g substrate, and Triton X-100 at 0.375 g/g substrate, which provided a maximum yield of reducing sugar 3828.86 µg/mL at 24-h incubation time.

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